

Bitwarden Install Guide

Bitwarden is a free and open-source password management service that stores sensitive information such as website credentials, payment data and notes in an encrypted vault.

Bitwarden has completed a security audit and cryptographic analysis from the German based firm Cure53.

The Bitwarden Security Assessment Report, dated November 8th, 2018 is available for download at:

<https://cdn.bitwarden.net/misc/Bitwarden%20Security%20Assessment%20Report.pdf>

Install Guide based on Bitwarden Version 2.12.0.

Downloads available at: <https://bitwarden.com/#download>

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The Information provided herein is for instructional purposes only.

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Setup Bitwarden Account

1. It is recommended to create an account first, before installing the software and/or browser extensions.

Business Download Help/FAQs Contact **Create Account** Log In ↗

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2. For additional security an email alias could be used which is only associated with this service. Example for Gmail users can add +alias to their normal email address (ex. johndoe@gmail.com) -> (johndoe+bit@gmail.com). NOTE: The Master Password is NOT recoverable is lost/forgotten.

Create Account

Email Address

You'll use your email address to log in.

Your Name

What should we call you?

Master Password

The master password is the password you use to access your vault. It is very important that you do not forget your master password. There is no way to recover the password in the event that you forget it.

Re-type Master Password

Master Password Hint (optional)

A master password hint can help you remember your password if you forget it.

By clicking the "Submit" button, you agree to the following policies: [Terms of Service](#), [Privacy Policy](#)

3. Sign in with new account

The image shows the Bitwarden login and account creation interface. At the top, the Bitwarden logo is displayed, followed by the text "Log in or create a new account to access your secure vault." Below this is a form with two main sections: "Email Address" and "Master Password". The "Email Address" field contains the text "johndoe+bit@gmail.com" and has a clear button (three dots in a square). The "Master Password" field is empty and has a clear button and a toggle icon (an eye) to the right. Below the password field is a link "Get master password hint". There is a checkbox labeled "Remember email" which is checked. At the bottom of the form are two buttons: a blue "Log In" button with a right-pointing arrow icon, and a white "Create Account" button with a pencil icon.

bitwarden

Log in or create a new account to access your secure vault.

Email Address

johndoe+bit@gmail.com

Master Password

Get master password hint

Remember email

Log In

Create Account

4. Click the Verify Mail -> “Send Mail” option to confirm your account. Note, there is also a separate automatic welcome email sent on sign-up. However, the verify email and send email option must still be completed to confirm your account. From your email client, the “Verify Email Address Now” link must be clicked on in the email.

Setup Two Step Login (2FA) with Bitwarden EMAIL OPTION

1. Click on Settings -> Two-step Login

2. Choose Two-step Login method. Note, the Authenticator App and Email options are available for free. Any changes will require you to reinput your Master Password.

Providers

	Authenticator App Use an authenticator app (such as Authy or Google Authenticator) to generate time-based verification codes.	Manage
	YubiKey OTP Security Key Premium Use a YubiKey to access your account. Works with YubiKey 4 series, 5 series, and NEO devices.	Manage
	Duo Premium Verify with Duo Security using the Duo Mobile app, SMS, phone call, or U2F security key.	Manage
	FIDO U2F Security Key Premium Use any FIDO U2F enabled security key to access your account.	Manage
	Email Verification codes will be emailed to you.	Manage

The screenshot shows the Bitwarden settings interface. A modal dialog titled "TWO-STEP LOGIN Authenticator App" is open, prompting the user to "Enter your master password to modify two-step login settings." The dialog contains a "Master Password" input field and two buttons: "Continue" and "Close". The background shows the "Two-step Login" settings page with a "View Recovery Code" button and a "Providers" section.

3. Click on Email Manage

Providers

	Authenticator App Use an authenticator app (such as Authy or Google Authenticator) to generate time-based verification codes.	Manage
	YubiKey OTP Security Key Premium Use a YubiKey to access your account. Works with YubiKey 4 series, 5 series, and NEO devices.	Manage
	Duo Premium Verify with Duo Security using the Duo Mobile app, SMS, phone call, or U2F security key.	Manage
	FIDO U2F Security Key Premium Use any FIDO U2F enabled security key to access your account.	Manage
	Email Verification codes will be emailed to you.	Manage

4. Confirm proper email address, click Send Email, but leave window open. Open email client in a separate window/client as you need to enter the 6 digit code sent your email here. Enter 6 digit code and click on “Enable”.

Saving Recovery Codes for Bitwarden

1. Click on View Recovery Code on the Two-step Login page and enter Master Password. A 32 character recovery code should display. This should be Printed and saved in a safe location (two copies in two safe locations is preferable).

Two-step Login

Secure your account by requiring an additional step when logging in.

⚠ WARNING

Enabling two-step login can permanently lock you out of your Bitwarden account. A recovery code allows you to access your account in the event that you can no longer use your normal two-step login provider (ex. you lose your device). Bitwarden support will not be able to assist you if you lose access to your account. We recommend you write down or print the recovery code and keep it in a safe place.

[View Recovery Code](#)

Domain Rules for Bitwarden

1. Click on Settings -> Domain Rules

1. Click on New Custom Domain and add the domains (separated by commas) and click Save. *The Example below is for the TORSTAR account to auto populate/login the saved account/password for three TORSTAR pages using thestar.com, mykawartha.com, thespec.com*****

Domain Rules

If you have the same login across multiple different website domains, you can mark the website as "equivalent". "Global" domains are ones already created for you by Bitwarden.

Custom Equivalent Domains

+ New Custom Domain

Enter a list of domains separated by commas. Only "base" domains are allowed. Do not enter subdomains. For example, enter "google.com" instead of "www.google.com". You can also enter "androidapp://package.name" to associate an android app with other website domains.

Save

Custom Equivalent Domains

thestar.com, mykawartha.com, thespec.com

+ New Custom Domain

Enter a list of domains separated by commas. Only "base" domains are allowed. Do not enter subdomains. For example, enter "google.com" instead of "www.google.com". You can also enter "androidapp://package.name" to associate an android app with other website domains.

Save

Bitwarden iOS Install

1. **Download Bitwarden Password Manager using the App Store. ***Confirm the name/description, the logo and description should exactly match. The search results for “Bitwarden” etc. may return other software *****

2. Enter Email Address & Master Password. Use the “Eye” icon to view the password your inputting and click on “Log In” in the top right to continue

3. If enabled, enter Verification Code and click on “Continue” in the top right.

Enter the 6 digit verification code from your authenticator app.

Verification Code

|

Remember me

Use another two-step login method

4. Bitwarden will ask to enable Push Notifications to sync the vault. If not enabled (ie. "Don't Allow" is selected), the vault can be synced manually under Settings -> Sync -> Sync Vault Now

Bitwarden iOS Password Autofill

To enable password autofill of passwords saved in Bitwarden and not in the native Apple Keychain.

1. Go to the Settings app, then select “Passwords and Accounts”

1. Then select “Autofill Passwords”, then select the “AutoFill Password” slider to on (if not already on), and select “Allow Filling From Bitwarden” checked, below. *Note both Keychain & Bitwarden can be enabled concurrently, however this is may lead to unexpected behaviour.*****

